

A two-Stage Fuzzy c-Means Clustering Algorithm for Lung Segmentation

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Abstract—Image processing techniques have proved to be invaluable in medical imaging as the various modalities produce large amounts of data which need to be analyzed in a timely manner. Segmentation is an essential step in many applications involving image processing. It partitions the image into segments corresponding to the anatomical objects in the image. This paper presents a fully automatic segmentation method for identifying the lungs in thoracic Computed Tomography (CT) images. The proposed method is based on Fuzzy c-Means (FCM) and operates in two stages. The first stage is the lung detection stage which identifies the location of the lung and is accomplished with 3-class FCM and connected components analysis. The second stage is the lung extraction stage which separates the pixels of the lungs from the rest of the image and is accomplished with 2-class FCM and morphology. Experiments were conducted using 100 CT images from two publicly available databases. The performance of the proposed method achieved a Dice coefficient index of 0.9907 ± 0.0054 , a Jaccard Similarity index of 0.9816 ± 0.0107 and an Accuracy of 0.9962 ± 0.0019 .

Keywords—Lung segmentation; Fuzzy c-Means; Computed Tomography; Medical Imaging;

I. INTRODUCTION

The advances in Computed Tomography (CT) have led to faster data acquisition speeds, higher spatial resolution images and improved signal-to-noise ratio. Several studies [1]–[3] have highlighted the importance of Thoracic Computed Tomography (CT) in pulmonary imaging as the clarity of the images enable better detection of the subtle changes in the lung tissue than in conventional chest X-ray images. However, these advances have also led to *data explosion* [4]. Large amounts of image data have to be analyzed and interpreted accurately in a short time. Manual methods of analysis are time-consuming and tedious and lead to errors and inconsistencies in the analysis due to fatigue. Computer-aided Detection (CAD) systems have been introduced into clinical practice to assist in image analysis. CAD systems use image processing and analysis techniques to analyze images and highlight suspicious areas signaling anomalies. Segmentation is an important step in image processing as it identifies the anatomical objects in the image and reduces the search space for disease detection in further stages of the CAD. Therefore, the accuracy of segmentation determines the accuracy of the CAD system.

Several authors have proposed lung segmentation methods based on thresholding due to the contrast between the lower attenuation values corresponding to the air and the higher attenuation values corresponding to the body and chest structures. Hu et al. [5] used optimal thresholding to separate voxels

in the lungs and surrounding background air from voxels within chest walls. The air within the lungs is distinguished from the surrounding non-body air by connected components labeling and topological analysis. Antonelli et al. [6] first eliminated the background air surrounding the chest before applying thresholding to separate pixels of the lung from the surrounding chest structures. Iqbal et al. [7] partitioned the image by selecting a threshold value which maximizes the within-class similarity. Jaffar et al. [8] developed a fuzzy entropy-based thresholding technique using Fuzzy c-Means with a different cluster validity measure. Due to different data acquisition conditions, the presence of artifacts and noise on CT images will cause these methods to perform poorly.

To eliminate the need of estimating a threshold value for each image, Shojaii et al. [9] proposed a marker-based watershed transform method to find the borders of the image, followed by smoothing the contour and filling the area within the borders. This method relies on knowledge of the range of attenuation values for various anatomical objects in the image for correct placement of internal and external markers which determine the success of the method. This could also be affected by intensity inhomogeneity in the CT image. Kothavari and Deepa [10] used a robust active shape matching (RASM) model which requires training using manually traced example images to accurately segment the lungs. The accuracy of this method is dependent on the amount of training examples and can lead to high computational costs.

This paper presents a method for automatic Lung segmentation from CT images. The method is based on Fuzzy c-Means (FCM) clustering algorithm [11] and the procedures are grouped into two main stages. First, a lung detection stage identifies the location of the lung with 3-class FCM and connected components analysis. Second, a lung extraction stage separates the pixels of the lungs from the rest of the image with 2-class FCM and morphology. Experimental results show the high performance of the proposed method in segmenting the lungs from the image.

The rest of the paper is organized as follows. Section II describes the proposed method in detail, Section III presents the experimental results of the method, Section IV provides the conclusion and future work.

II. PROPOSED METHOD

The proposed method is in two stages. The first stage involves detecting the location of the lungs in the image.

The image is split into non-overlapping blocks and the mean intensity value of each block is calculated and stored in a dataset. This dataset is clustered into three classes with FCM. Next, connected components analysis is used to label the components in the image and contextual information is used to identify the lungs. The second stage involves extracting the pixels of the lungs from the rest of the image. The image is cropped to contain only the lung region detected from the first stage. This cropped image is clustered into two classes to create a binary mask. Morphology is used to fill the holes in the lungs corresponding to high density structures. An overview of the proposed method is shown in Fig. 1. The remaining parts of the section give details of the proposed method.

Fig. 1: Overview of the proposed method

A. Lung Detection

The image is first split into non-overlapping blocks. The purpose of splitting the image is to reduce the computation time involved in clustering the image. Let I represent the original CT image containing $M \times N$ pixels. The image is split into $M/p \times N/q$ non-overlapping blocks of size $p \times q$. Let $b_{k,l}$ be the $(k,l)^{th}$ block. The mean $\bar{b}_{k,l}$ of each block is calculated as

$$\bar{b}_{k,l} = \frac{1}{p \times q} \sum_{i=0}^{p-1} \sum_{j=0}^{q-1} I_{i+p \times k, j+q \times l} \quad (1)$$

The mean of each block in the image is stored in a dataset. This dataset is partitioned into three classes with FCM. Let M represent the set of data containing the mean intensity value of each block $b_{k,l}$. Each $m \in M$ represents the pixels within the block $b_{k,l}$. M is clustered into $c = 3$ fuzzy partitions. The highest fuzzy membership is selected for each $m \in M$, and the cluster to which m belongs to determines the membership of the pixels in each region $b_{k,l}$. This produces a clustered image showing the membership of each pixel in image I .

Connected components analysis using 8-neighborhood connectivity is used to identify and label components in the clustered image. Contextual properties including the area and

the bounding box of each component is measured and physical characteristics of the lung such as height to width ratio, proximity of components and their relative sizes are used to detect the lungs from the clustered image. Figure 2 shows the lungs detected in the clustered image with the detected lungs enclosed by bounding boxes.

Fig. 2: The result of lung detection stage (a) original CT image (b) clustered image showing detected lungs (enclosed in red bounding box)

B. Lung Extraction

The second stage begins by cropping the image to include the only the detected lung region. This is done by removing the regions outside the height of the highest bounding box and the width of the extreme left and right corners of the bounding boxes surrounding the detected lungs. The purposes include: (1) it eliminates the air surrounding the chest wall which has the same range of attenuation values as the lungs and (2) it reduces the computation time as only a smaller part of the image will serve as input for the next stage of clustering.

The cropped image is partitioned into $c = 2$ fuzzy partitions with FCM. Let J represent the cropped image. The highest fuzzy membership is selected for each pixel $j \in J$. A binary mask is produced which separates the pixels of the lung from the rest of the image.

Fig. 3: The steps of lung extraction stage (a) cropped image (b) clustered image (c) binary mask after morphology

The lungs contain high density structures such as the blood vessels and juxtaleural nodules which appear as holes in the lung. To obtain the final mask for segmentation, morphology is used to fill the lungs and the high intensity structures are marked as belonging to the lung. The steps of the lung extraction stage is shown in Fig. 3. Fig. 4 shows the lungs extracted from the image.

III. RESULTS

The proposed method was tested using images from Lung Image Database Consortium and Image Database Resource Initiative (LIDC-IDRI) database [12] and Lung Test Images

Fig. 4: The result of lung extraction stage (a) original CT image (b) image showing extracted lungs

from Motol Environment (Lung TIME) database [13]. LIDC-IDRI database consists of 1018 cases of diagnostic and lung cancer screening thoracic CT scans with annotated lesions taken from different scanners supplied by different vendors. The Lung TIME database consists of two parts. The first part contains data from adolescent patients with 148 scans, 5mm slice thickness and 1mm slice spacing. The second part contains 9 scans with 5mm thickness and 5mm slice spacing. Images that pose a challenge to thresholding using the method in [14] are selected from the LIDC-IDRI database. The images from Lung TIME were selected randomly. A total of 100 images were selected for the experiments. Each image is of size 512×512 and stored in DICOM format.

The proposed method has been implemented in MATLAB[®] using the Image Processing toolbox on a PC with Intel Core(TM) i7-4770S @ 3.10Ghz, 8.00GB RAM. The average time taken to segment each 512×512 image is about 0.2520 secs.

The performance of the proposed method was measured with Dice coefficient [15], Jaccard similarity [16] and Accuracy by comparing ground truth masks (G) against the segmentation results (S). The ground truth masks were created using semi-automatic tools [17] and an atlas of the chest [18]. The Dice coefficient and Jaccard Similarity measure the amount of overlap between G and S. The index ranges from zero to one with an index of zero signifying no overlap and an index of one signifying perfect overlap. The Dice coefficient (DC) is given as

$$DC = 2 \frac{|G \cap S|}{|G| + |S|} \quad (2)$$

The Jaccard similarity (JS) is given as

$$JS = \frac{|G \cap S|}{|G \cup S|} \quad (3)$$

Accuracy measures the reliability of the proposed method to isolate the lungs from the image and is given as

$$Accuracy = \frac{TP + TN}{TP + TN + FP + FN} \quad (4)$$

where TP is the number of True Positives, FP is the number of False Positives, TN is the number of True Negatives and FN is the number of False Negatives.

Table I shows the performance of the proposed method using the performance metrics in each database and the average performance on all the selected images from both databases.

TABLE I: Results using Performance Metrics

Data Set	DC	JS	Accuracy
LIDC	0.9897	0.9797	0.9967
Lung TIME	0.9916	0.9834	0.9956
Mean	0.9907 ± 0.0054	0.9816 ± 0.0107	0.9962 ± 0.0019

Table II compares the results of the proposed method with other CT Lung segmentation methods from literature.

TABLE II: Comparison with other methods in Literature

Method	JS	DC
Massoptier et al [19]	–	97.42%
Pu et al [20]	$95.1\% \pm 2.0$	–
Abdollahi et al [21]	–	$96.0\% \pm 1.10$
Guo et al [22]	$92.1\% \pm 4.5$	–
Wei et al [23]	95.24%	–
Proposed Method	$98.16\% \pm 1.07$	$99.07\% \pm 0.54$

Fig. 5 shows the visual results obtained using the proposed method. The segmented lungs are marked in green.

IV. CONCLUSION

In this paper, an automatic lung segmentation method has been developed which accurately segments the lungs in a CT image. The proposed method uses FCM in two stages by first detecting the location of the lung and then extracting the lungs from the image. Techniques to achieve a faster runtime include splitting the image into non-overlapping blocks and using the mean of each block as input for the clustering in the first stage and cropping the image to include only the detected lung region for the clustering in the second stage. Experiments were carried out by comparing the segmentation results with ground truth masks and with results from literature. The experimental results show that the proposed method is capable of accurate segmentations. Future work will involve improvements to the border around the hilar region of the lung where the bronchi and major vessels enter the lung.

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Fig. 5: Example images showing the visual performance of the proposed method on (a) images from LIDC-IDRI database and (b) images from Lung TIME database. The segmented lungs are shown in green

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